

NATURAL SEMANTIC METALANGUAGE APPROACH

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Annotation: *The study of the written word expands well beyond the action of learning another language. Behind the many courses we take to understand the many different tongues in the world are entire groups of professional linguists, studying the structure of words and sentences as a way to understand their cultural roots, how they have evolved over time and how they compare or measure up to other languages.*

Although there are many approaches taken to these kind of studies, there has been one recent addition to the list that seems to be one of the most comprehensive and well developed systems that has come to the light in years.

This approach of course is the Natural Semantic Metalanguage. This article is concerned with the study of Natural Semantic Metalanguage approach.

Despite it's long and intimidating name, the N.S.M. approach looks forward to do the complete opposite and actually simplify the way cross-linguistics and cross-cultural semantics are studied. It's basically a small mini-language on itself that corresponds to the common core of all other languages.

Key words: *Natural Semantic Metalanguage approach, Semantic Primes, Lexical Semantics, Semantic Molecules, Semantic Templates, Explication.*

Natural Semantic Metalanguage approach is regarded as a process in which meaning is the key element to insightful and explanatory descriptions of most linguistic phenomena, phonetics and phonology excepted. It is also the process which requires a decompositional system of meaning based on empirically established universal semantic primes.¹

Goddard points out that meaning, which can be the bridge between language and cognition, and between language and culture, is considered vital element in NSM approach. Simply, NSM can be understood that it is a clearer and simpler explication of complex meanings. In order to explicate meaning in a simpler way, applying reductive paraphrase is put forward by a number of scholars. In this process, speaker's words are explicated in the metalanguage of semantic primes. According to Goddard's viewpoint NSM is the only approach

to employ paraphrase in a strict sense. Additionally, he claims that many other approaches tend to use decompositional terms to describe meaning which causes an obvious confusion between paraphrase and description. Paraphrasing demonstrates an insider perspective which makes meaning easy to comprehend while description intends to give a mental image of something experienced.

SEMANTIC PRIMES

Semantic primes are considered to be one of the aspects of NSM approach which have been under the discussion for several years. They are defined as lexical universals in the sense of having an exact translation in every human language.² Explication of semantic primes can be much easier to understand with the help of examples: considering the word "know", in sentence like "Jane knows

¹ Goddard, Cliff. ["The Natural Semantic Metalanguage Approach"](#) (PDF). Griffith University. Archived from the original (PDF) on 5 June 2014. Retrieved 27 May 2013

² Goddard, Cliff. ["The Natural Semantic Metalanguage Approach"](#) (PDF). Internet Archive Wayback Machine. Oxford University Press. Archived from the original (PDF) on 23 July 2017. Retrieved 13 October 2018

something about me”. How could we paraphrase the meaning of “know” in this context by using simpler words? The idiom “find out” will not do, because it is more complex and difficult to understand than “know” in the first place. The only acceptable explication would be something like “I did something, so that she is aware of something which belongs to me”, but it fails because there are many actions a person could undertake because of being familiar with something which belongs to someone. On the other hand, if we use the word “say”, as in “Jane said something about me”, it seems readily paraphrase by using simpler words. We can analyze in the following way:

- Jane said something about me
- Because she wanted to say something about me
- She asked something about me

According to this process, “say” is a good candidate for the status of semantic prime. As seen polysemy is frequently a complication when trying to identify primes and match them across languages. Over the fifteen years of investigation researchers have gathered a lot of data about common patterns of polysemy. In this table, several widely accepted patterns are demonstrated:

Some common polysemies involving exponents of semantic primes:

Say	Speak, make sounds	Thai, Mandarin, Yankunytjatjara, Kalam
Think	Worry, long for, intend	Mandarin, Swedish
Want	Like, love	Spanish, Ewe, Bunuba
Happen	Arrive, appear	French, Ewe, Mangaaba-Mbula
Do	Make	Spanish, Malay, Arrernte, Samoan, Kalam, Amharic
Before	First, go ahead, front	Lao, Samoan, Kayardild, Ewe, Mangaaba-Mbula
Feel	Taste, smell, hold an opinion	Malay, Acehnese, Ewe, French, Mandarin
Words	What is said, message, speech language	Yankunytjatjara, Korean, Mangaaba-Mbula, Malay

Source: studies in Goddard and Wierzbicka 1994.

LEXICAL SEMANTICS

When it comes to discuss NSM analysis, we have to point out lexical semantics which has been under the deep discussion. Goddard claims that the validity of NSM explications can be tested on the basis of two main conditions: substitutability in a broad sense and well-formedness. Additionally, it is adequate whether explications conform to a coherence condition. In other words, they have to make a sense as a

whole, with appropriate chains of anaphora, co-reference, casual links, etc.

On this occasion, it is vital to clarify what semantic explications are. They are referred as explanatory paraphrases which can be framed in the metalanguage of simple and universal semantic primes. For instance, the following explications show a semantic description for the verbs “help” and “steal”.

Someone X helped someone Y

Someone X did Something for Someone

Y

Because of this, something good happened to someone Y

Because of this, someone Y is thankful for someone X

Someone X stole something Y

Someone X did something to something Y

Because of this, something happened to something Y at the same time

It happened in one moment

After this, something Y was not in its place anymore.

According to NSM research, the meanings of emotion terms involve feelings linked with a characteristic and prototypical cognitive scenario involving thoughts and wants. The scenario serves as a kind of “reference situation” by which the nature of the associated feeling can be identified.³ For example, “happy” is linked prototypically with the thought something very good is happening now, sad is linked with the thought something bad happened. It would be clearer if we look through the explication of the adjectives “angry” and “depressed”.

X felt angry

Someone can feel something like this when this someone thinks like this:

I know something bad happened

I do not think something like this to happen

I know that I cannot do anything

The prototypical cognitive scenario involves an awareness that something bad happened and an acceptance of the fact that one do not think something like this to happen. This is compatible with the wide range of use of “angry”: for example that I may feel angry when someone did something wrong or there is an injustice in my workplace.

Someone X felt depressed.

Someone X felt something bad

Someone can feel something like this when this someone thinks like this for some time.

Some very bad things happened to me

These bad things last for a long time

I wanted bad things not to happen

I always think about these bad things although it is wrong

The way of explication of being depressed differs from being angry.

1. Being depressed requires someone X to experience some bad things

2. Depressed conveys a stronger negative evaluation when it is compared to its synonyms

3. Depressed has a more personal character: someone or something makes someone X angry, if someone is depressed, bad things have happened to one personally

4. Being depressed can be within a longer duration of time while being angry happens at an exact time.

SEMANTIC MOLECULES

As far as NSM researchers concerned, some kinds of concepts (emotions, values, speech acts and interpersonal relations) can be explicated in a simpler way than the others (artifacts, animals, plants, human activities and etc.) This is because that the former can be explicated directly while the later can only be explicated in stages using intermediate-level semantic molecules.⁴ For example, the concept of plants is necessary in the explications of trees, flowers and other species. Body part concepts are required in verbs like eat, punch, run, speak. According to the above-mentioned data, we can give definition of semantic molecules. It is regarded as packet of semantic components which exist as the meaning of a lexical unit.

The analysis of body part words can be clear example to indicate semantic molecule.

Eyes (someone's eyes)

Two parts of the body

³ Goddard, Cliff; Wierzbicka, Anna, eds. (2002). *Meaning and Universal Grammar: Theory and Empirical Findings*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.

⁴ Goddard, Cliff. "[Semantic Molecules](#)". *NSM Homepage*. Retrieved 2 February 2018.

These parts are on the face
These parts are like something round
Because people`s bodies have these two parts, they can see everything
Nose (Someone`s nose)
One part of someone`s body
This part is on the face
This part has two nostrils
Because people`s bodies have this part, they can breathe

Now consider some shape descriptors which are both visual and tangible. Something round (table, ball, globus)

When someone sees this thing, someone can think about it like this:

This shape descriptor is not like others
Because it does not have any corner
If someone`s hands touch it, someone can think about it in the same way.

It is interesting to note about the number of productive semantic molecules. For English, there are may be more than 150-200. They are classified according to the following categories:

- A) Parts of the body: hands, mouth, legs
- B) Physical descriptors: long, round, flat, hard, sharp, straight
- C) Physical activities: eat, drink, sit
- D) Physical acts: kill, pick up, catch
- E) Expressive/communicative actions: laugh, sing, write, read
- F) Ethnogeometrical terms: edges, ends
- G) Life-form words: animal, bird, fish, tree
- H) Natural environment: the ground, the sky, water, fire, day, night
- D) Materials: wood, stone, metal, glass, paper
- J) Mechanical parts: wheel, pipe, wire, engine, electricity, machine
- K) Basic social categories and kin roles: men, women, children, mother and father
- L) Important cultural concepts: money, book, color, number. ⁵

⁵ Goddard, Cliff. "[Semantic Molecules](#)". *NSM Homepage*. Retrieved 2 February 2018.

SEMANTIC TEMPLATES

The next point of the investigation is dedicated to the semantic templates. They are regarded as the structured set of component types shared by words of a particular semantic class – often applicable across many languages.⁶ The concept was first introduced by Wierzbicka, in the form of explications for artifact and natural kind terms. In recent years, many scholars have done several surveys and researches on this concept. Goddard and Wierzbicka elaborated and applied semantic templates to adjectives and verbs, Rapaport Hovav and Levin introduced the explications of lexical templates in other frameworks. It would be useful to explain semantic templates with the help of examples. Let`s see the explications for animal terms which can be divided into the following sections:

- a) Category
- b) Habitat
- c) Size
- d) Body
- e) Behavior
- f) Sound
- g) Relation to people

⁶ Wierzbicka, Anna (1972). *Semantic Primitives*. Athenäum

The explication of “LION”

Category	Animal of one kind
Habitat	Animal of this kind can live in wild nature
Size	Big
Body	They have a round head, ears and eyes. They have four legs and tail Male lions have mane while females do not
Behavior	This kind of animals are wild
Sound	Roaring
Relation to people	They sometimes hunt human People usually feel fear of this kind of animals

The explication of “HORSE”

Category	Animal of one kind
Habitat	Animal of this kind can live both domestically and wildly
Size	Big
Body	They have ears, eyes, a nose They have four legs and tail They have mane
Behavior	Fast, loyal, but sometimes aggressive
Sound	Neighing
Relation to people	This kind of animal can live with people and they can show their loyalty, they are friendly toward people.

Overall, it can be said that, the Natural Semantic Metalanguage approach proves to be an amazing tool that has been widely used in the creation of dictionaries and break the barriers of communication between countries and cultures.

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